

Waggle movement as a visual mate-finding signal in Triozid psyllids

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Three species of psyllids within Triozidae have been recorded to exhibit a wagging or twitching movement of their abdomens. Here, I present video of one of these species. This behaviour suggests single adult and dual adult wagging may be a sexual signalling behaviour, similar in function to the already described volatile and vibrational signalling described in other psyllid species.

Introduction

Psyllids are small, mobile insects capable of both walking and flight movement as adults. They reproduce sexually, thus signalling mating readiness and mate-finding are important for them. Almost all work has been conducted on pest species, primarily as a monitoring tool or to determine the opportunity to disrupt mating and therefore population growth.

Currently, mate finding is thought to include visual, volatile and acoustic/vibrational sensing mechanisms (Krysan 1990; Wenninger and Hall 2007; Wenninger et al. 2009; Lubanga et al. 2014).

Volatiles are known to be detected by psyllids and used as a means of detecting host plant suitability (Patt and Sétamou 2010; Davis et al. 2012; Mann et al. 2012; Yuvaraj et al. 2013). Volatiles are also known to attract males to females (Soroker et al. 2004; Horton et al. 2008; Wenninger et al. 2008; Guédot et al. 2010), including a differential response by males to mated or virgin females (Guédot et al. 2013). It seems likely that sensing these volatiles/pheromones assists in host/mating discovery at a distance.

Acoustic signalling (Percy et al. 2006; Tishechkin 2007; Eden et al. 2015) and similar signals via vibration through the substrate (Mankin et al. 2015; Lujo et al. 2016; Liao and Yang 2017) have been reported as mate-finding stimuli. That these signals are indeed mating signals is evident by individual insect responses, and they are sufficiently specific and stable to provide a phylogenetic signal (Percy et al. 2006). They may occur as signals alternating between males

and females, a duet of two-sided communication. Clearly these are close-range signals.

Psyllids have prominent eyes and respond to colour, favouring certain colours over others (Brennan and Weinbaum 2001; Hall et al. 2007; Taylor et al. 2014). Visual mating stimuli are suggested too. For example, *Cacopsylla pyricola* males appear to recognise females at a relatively close distance and mating is essentially absent in the dark (Krysan 1990). Visual cues are clearly beneficial, but not essential, for *Diaphorina citri* since some mating may still occur during the dark (Wenninger and Hall 2007).

Large body movements have been reported in three Triozid species. This movement in the New Zealand native *Powellia vitreoradiata*, formerly *Trioza vitreoradiata* (Burckhardt and Ouvrard 2012), has been described as “the whole body is continually flicked from side to side” (Carter 1949). In another New Zealand species, *Trioza panacis* “the abdomen of the adult psyllid continually twitches from side to side” (Martin 2018). *Trioza brevigenea* “raises its abdomen... and then moves it from side to side like a dog wagging its tail” (Hodel et al. 2016). No indication of purpose for this movement is indicated for any of these species.

The psyllid *P. vitreoradiata* is commonly known as the pittosporum psyllid. *Pittosporum* plants, also natives of New Zealand, have become popular in horticultural uses as specimen trees/shrubs and formal or informal hedging. The psyllid is widespread and common on plants of this genus (Tuthill 1952), including on urban plantings. Eggs and nymphs are

Video 1 Solitary female *P. vitreoradiata* exhibiting waggling movement.

Video 2 Solitary male *P. vitreoradiata* exhibiting waggling movement.

generally clustered on new-flush growth, but adults are generally far more widely dispersed on the plants. Here I illustrate some observations of the waggling movement of this psyllid.

Observation

Observation of individuals on these shrubs indicates that they frequently exhibit a prominent sideways movement, or wagggle, of their abdomen and wings. In general, this is observed in solitary insects that appear to be feeding, or at least stationary, in both females (Video 1) and males (Video 2). This waggling movement has also been noted when on non-host plant species (pers obs).

A recent chance observation of two individuals exhibiting semi-synchronised waggles suggests this could be a mate-finding behaviour (Video 3). This particular observation was made on a garden shrub of *Pittosporum tenuifolium* in Christchurch, New Zealand. Although clear copulatory behaviour occurs, this is very brief and these are both male insects. However, this also shows the waggling movement is possible while walking.

Discussion

The synchronicity suggests something analogous to the duets of acoustic/vibration reported previously, but using visual cues. The prominent movements made during the waggling dance suggest an indicator at close range of confirmation of readiness to mate. Like the vibrational calling, both males and females exhibit this waggling behaviour.

Video 3 Male *P. vitreoradiata* exhibiting semi-synchronised waggling movement, including one walking towards the other and male-male attempted copulation. Videos are embedded but also available as separate files from the doi link below.

Homosexual mating behaviour in insects has long been observed (Laboulbène 1859; de Kerville 1896). Various reasons for this behaviour have been suggested, such as mistaken identification or incompetence/inexperience in mating (Scharf and Martin 2013) (Tishechkin 2007; Stockton et al. 2017). Indiscriminate male sexual behaviours could explain an increase in male-male mounting in entomopathogenic fungi-infected locusts (Clancy et

al. 2017) and polyandry mating in psyllids (Lubanga et al. 2018). *C. pyricola* in North American pear orchards have been observed attempting copulation with winged aphids and approaching bits of small debris, presumably thinking they might be female psyllids (D Horton, pers comm, October 2019).

In the context of vibrational duet mating signalling, a male psyllid may respond as “a possible defensive mechanism against eavesdropping competitors” (Liao and Yang 2017). Multiple males may respond with vibrational calling into a fused chorus, presumably confusing each other, or as dominance/hierarchical behaviour, including extravagant displays (Tishechkin 2007). Male psyllid volatiles have been described as

being attractive to other males (Guédot et al. 2010), or at least not repellent (Wenninger et al. 2008).

Conclusion

The complex host plant environment, especially where adults are widely dispersed on a plant, indicates a need for mate-finding signalling. The observations noted here suggest that the waggle movement, both by males and females, adds a relatively long-range visual signal as a component of mate signalling.

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